

IMPORTANT INFORMATION ABOUT VITAMINS

Akhundjonova Khakima Abdumannabovna

Kholbobaeva Shakhnoza Asadullaevna

Assistants of the Central Asian Medical University

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Abstract: Vitamins are important biologically active substances necessary for the growth and development of the entire organism. Since vitamins enter our body mainly with food, it is very important to know what foods contain them and what diseases occur when they are deficient.

Key words: vitamin B1 or thiamine, vitamin B2 or riboflavin, vitamin B6 or pyridoxine, vitamin B12 or cyanocobalamin, vitamin P or rutin, vitamin PP or niacin.

Аннотация: Витамины – важные биологически активные вещества, необходимые для роста и развития всего организма. Поскольку витамины попадают в наш организм преимущественно с пищевыми продуктами, очень важно знать, в каких продуктах они содержатся и какие заболевания возникают при их недостаточности.

Ключевые слова: витамин B1 или тиамин, витамин B2 или рибофлавин, витамин B6 или пиридоксин, витамин B12 или цианокобаламин, витамин P или рутин, витамин PP или никотиновая кислота.

In everyday life, a person can eat different things. It contains various substances and vitamins. Vitamins A, B, B1, B2, B6, B12, C, D, PP, K are extremely necessary for the human body. Their influence plays a very important role in the functioning of the human body. A deficiency of one of these vitamins in the human body creates conditions for the occurrence of various diseases.[1]

Vitamin B1 (thiamine), studied by K. Funk in 1912, its name thiamine comes from the Greek term “thione-sulfur”. Thiamine is found in many foods. It is mainly found in the husks and husks (bran) of grain. Thiamine is important for carbohydrate metabolism in the body; If food is rich in carbohydrates, more thiamine is required for their absorption. Without thiamine, polyneuritis occurs. In the absence or deficiency of this vitamin in the body, a serious disease of the nervous system appears - vitamin deficiency, as well as decreased intestinal motility, constipation, muscle relaxation, and decreased physical and mental performance.[2]

Function of vitamin B1. Vitamin B1 (thiamine) balances protein and carbohydrate metabolism in the body. This vitamin softens carbohydrate

metabolism and is necessary for the functioning of the nervous system, cells and gastrointestinal tract. In the human and animal body, they are converted into thiamine pyrophosphate, act as a special biocatalyst for the decarboxylation reaction of pyruvic acid, eliminate the strong toxic substance pyruvic acid, and normalize the excitation of the nervous system. [3] **Natural Sources of Vitamin B1:** This is a water-soluble vitamin, so when you cook such foods, the water in them is also rich in this vitamin. This vitamin is destroyed by soda. The daily requirement of this vitamin is 1-2 mg. What foods contain this vitamin: **wholemeal bread, cereals (buckwheat, oatmeal, juices), peas, soybeans, brewer's yeast, liver, beef. Its natural sources are yeast, especially brewer's yeast, bread yeast (yeast), cereals, grains, bread (especially black), and vegetables.**

Vitamin B2 or riboflavin Vitamin B2 (riboflavin) balances the process of cellular metabolism and processes in the surface layer of the skin, and is also involved in the respiration process. Riboflavin - is involved in the growth process and is one of the growth factors. With a lack of this vitamin, acne will appear on the face. Riboflavin enters the body with food; if there is a lack of riboflavin in food, cracks in the corners of the mouth, lips, hair loss, conjunctivitis and blepharitis are observed, this can cause inflammation of the mucous membranes, hair loss, and dizziness. With a long-term deficiency of this vitamin, the skin loses its smoothness and begins to look like old skin. Vitamin B2 deficiency is characterized by growth retardation, hair loss, damage to the mucous membranes (especially the corners of the mouth), decreased performance, impaired hemoglobin synthesis. [4] **Sources of riboflavin:** Important sources of its nutrition are - **milk and dairy products, fish, eggs, liver, cereals (buckwheat and oatmeal) and bread. The daily requirement of vitamin B2 is 2-5 mg.**

Vitamin B6 (pyridoxine) performs important functions in the body. Essential for the nervous system and protein metabolism. It ensures normal digestion of proteins and fats and plays an important role in nitrogen metabolism. This vitamin is taken for hair loss and skin inflammation. **The main products containing vitamin B6 are liver, beans, cereals (buckwheat, bough), wheat flour, yeast. The daily requirement for vitamin B6 is 1-2 mg.** Pyridoxine (vitamin B6) is found in many products of plant and animal origin: yeast, wheat germ, liver, fish, beef and legumes. There is a lot of this vitamin in liver, milk, potatoes, carrots, eggs, butter, rice, wheat, cabbage. If there is a lack of pyridoxine in the body, children will not grow, the functions of the

gastrointestinal tract will be impaired, and anemia will occur. Pregnant women experience stomatitis, skin inflammation, irritability, and insomnia. The amount of pyridoxine necessary for the human body is produced under the influence of intestinal bacteria.[5]

Vitamin B12 (cyanocobalamin) is a highly biologically active substance. Methionine is involved in the synthesis of nucleic acids and hematopoiesis. **Cyanocobalamin is found in products of animal origin. These are: liver, meat, some types of fish, cheese, etc. Vitamin B12 is also produced by intestinal flora.** The daily requirement for vitamin B12 is 15-20 mcg. There is especially a lot of cyanocobalamin in beef liver.

Vitamin B9 or folic acid. Folic acid is found in wholemeal flour and bread products made from this flour, cereals (buckwheat, oats, soot), beans, cauliflower, mushrooms, liver, found in the country. cheese, cheese and caviar. It is important to know that 80-90% of the vitamins in the product are lost as a result of cooking. Folic acid is involved in the metabolism and synthesis of certain amino acids, as well as in the synthesis of nucleic acids, and strengthens bones. hematopoietic function of the bone marrow and helps absorb vitamin B12. **Folic acid is found in large quantities in foods of plant and animal origin, especially liver, kidneys and green leafy vegetables. Intestinal microorganisms synthesize folic acid in large quantities. Folic acid and pregnancy.** Even if not now, a woman planning a pregnancy in the coming years also needs folic acid. Because the fetus's need for folic acid begins from the first days of pregnancy, when the woman does not even know about pregnancy.[6] In order not to miss this important period, it is advisable for all women who have a chance of becoming pregnant to take folic acid every other day after consulting a doctor.

Vitamin P or rutin Vitamin P (Rutin, Quercetin, Hesperidin) - this vitamin belongs to the group of flavonoids. In plants, it usually coexists with vitamin C. Vitamin P has a positive effect on blood vessels, increases the effectiveness of vitamin C, and strengthens the walls of blood vessels. [7] As a result, it prevents their inflammation and improves blood clotting. Quercetin slows down the growth of tumor cells. It is especially used in breast cancer and blood cancer. Hesperidin is widely used to strengthen the walls of blood vessels in case of varicose veins (varicose veins, hemorrhoids). This vitamin is found in **blueberries, elderberries, linden, black currants, and lemon zest. Daily body requirement:** Rutin – 30 mg, Quercetin – 15 mg, Hesperidin – 100 mg.

Vitamin PP or nicotinic acid. Vitamin PP (nicotinic acid) was isolated by K. Funk in 1911 and turned out to be ineffective in treating beriberi disease in pigeons. [8] Later, when a scientist named Goldoyenger discovered that it cured pellagra, it was added to the list of vitamins. The term pellagra comes from the Italian word pela agra, meaning skin, and causes dermatitis, diarrhea and even dementia.

Function of vitamin PP. Vitamin PP reacts to water metabolism in the skin and dilates blood vessels. Nicotinamide, nicotinic acid (vitamin PP) are involved in cellular respiration, protein metabolism, accelerate the digestion of plant proteins in the body, normalize gastric secretion and motility, improve the composition of secretions and juices produced by the pancreas and liver. stabilizes work. This vitamin is used in the treatment of insomnia and neuroses.[9]

Nicotinic acid deficiency...

Pellagra disease occurs when there is not enough niacin in the body. In addition, mental retardation, depression, diarrhea, fatigue, insomnia, low blood sugar, low energy are observed.[10] **Sources of vitamin PP:** poultry, beef, liver There is a lot of it in kidneys, yeast, rice and wheat bran. Vitamin PP is also found in safflower, St. John's wort, sage, wheat bran, carrots, mushrooms, cranberries and blueberries.

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